
bridging the gap between the land and the sea in a virtual environment for
innovative teaching and community involvement in the science of marine and coastal geohazard

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Integration of seamless 3D models for geohazard assessment and management practices in a climatically sensitive coastal environment

BridgET Project Result 07

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BridgET: Bridging the gap between the land and the sea in a virtual environment for innovative teaching and community involvement in the science of climate change-induced marine and coastal geohazard

Erasmus+ Programme

Key Action: KA2 - Partnerships for cooperation and exchanges of practices Action

Type: Cooperation partnerships in higher education

BridgET Consortium:

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PROJECT RESULT REPORT

07 - Integration of seamless 3D models for geohazard assessment and management practices in a climatically sensitive coastal environment

Introduction

This project result presents an interactive Story Map that showcases the integration of multisource and multiscale geospatial data collected on Magoodhoo Island, a coral island in Faafu atoll in the Maldives. The platform highlights how advanced digital mapping tools can be applied to support geohazard assessment and coastal management in vulnerable low-lying island environments.

The resource is publicly accessible here:

☞ <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/873e525df3af4ecc8f7c6e1861b1139e>

The Story Map is the result of intensive field activities conducted during the project's third summer school, which focused on integrating data from various sources and scales. Participants and researchers collected new datasets using a range of techniques, including:

- UAV-based photogrammetry
- Multibeam bathymetry
- Underwater photogrammetry

These data were then integrated into seamless 3D models covering both the terrestrial and marine environments of Magoodhoo Island and its surrounding reef. In addition to new acquisitions, the platform also incorporates previous datasets collected during earlier expeditions and research initiatives on the island (including Multibeam, AUV data, and satellite derived bathymetry) ensuring a more complete representation of the emerged and submerged landscapes.

The Story Map presents this information in an accessible, layered format that combines 3D visualizations, interactive maps, photos, videos, and explanatory text. It provides a comprehensive perspective on the island's geomorphology, environmental vulnerabilities, and the role of 3D modeling in supporting climate resilience and hazard mitigation strategies.

This resource is:

- Freely accessible online
- Designed for use in educational and outreach activities, especially in courses on remote sensing, geohazards, and coastal management
- A practical example of data integration for applied environmental analysis

Intended to support both teaching and stakeholder engagement in the context of climate-sensitive coastal environments

List of Deliverables:

Deliverable 7.1: Integration of seamless 3D models for geohazard assessment and management practices in a climatically sensitive coastal environment: A story map at:

<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/873e525df3af4ecc8f7c6e1861b1139e>

1. Project Result 07 – Deliverable overview

Below is a description of the deliverable produced as part of project result “Toolkit for virtual reality exploration of underwater environments”.

Deliverable 7.1 – Integration of seamless 3D models for geohazard assessment and management practices in a climatically sensitive coastal environment: a story map

Description: An integrated VR toolkit consisting of a web-based Story Map. The resource presents underwater and coastal geological sites using 360° videos, maps, and 3D models, based on ROV-acquired data. It is designed for immersive education and science communication, and is freely accessible online.

Type of Output: Web-based Interactive Resource

Language: English

Access/Format: Online Platform

Access Level: Public

Attachment/link: <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/873e525df3af4ecc8f7c6e1861b1139e>

Deliverable 7.1

Integration of seamless 3D models for geohazard assessment and management practices in a climatically sensitive coastal environment

<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/873e525df3af4ecc8f7c6e1861b1139e>